

ISic3655

I.Sicily inscription 3655

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

conglomerate

Object

stone

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Monte Alburchia di Gangi

Provenance

found not far from the fattoria of P. Glorioso (so Manganaro (1965))

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Gangi, private property

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 200 tav.71.2

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